

Discrimination of Women Worker with Disabilities

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Abstract— This study uses the qualitative approach of the Straussian version of the grounded theory method. Data collection uses unstructured interviews, non-participant observation, and fgd (group discussion forum). The researchers wanted to see how discrimination experienced by women workers in disability in the city of Malang. Women with disabilities need to be pitied affects the psychology of women with disabilities, due to being labeled that they need to be pitied and become a doctrine that women with disabilities are useless.

Keywords— Discrimination, Women Worker, Women with Disabilities.

I. INTRODUCTION

Malang city is the largest city in the East Java province. Increasing mobility has an impact on life's needs. Especially experienced by women with disabilities in the city of Malang. The high level of violence against women with disabilities is not a product of "disability as vulnerability", but is a consequence of inherent segregation, poverty, physical, economic and social dependence created by persons with disabilities (1). Community structures regard disability as a medical problem, people with disabilities are considered unable to survive independently or participate in society. Not surprisingly, this has led to segregation and loss of fate for persons with disabilities. Disabled children are sent to special schools and persons with disabilities receive medical and rehabilitation care in separate settings namely repair or cure, while ignoring the wishes of persons with disabilities. When persons with disabilities are given benefits, it is often based on the opinion that they cannot work (4).

Latuny (3) explains that the dual role of family women can also have a positive impact, due to increased welfare in the family. This is realized if it is able to maintain balance, harmony and harmony with the environment that can be achieved on the basis of understanding, awareness and sacrifice of the husband or partner. Active family involvement and work environment in a process of achieving goals carried out by women who play a dual role, can be organized based on adequate capabilities of each individual, so that for women who have a dual role, all behaviors and social actions taken can lead on stability and harmonization in the family. A strong desire to actualize himself, and have the ability to do positive things that can bring success in the world of work and family in a balanced manner (3).

Women and girls with disabilities are more likely to face greater discrimination in accessing opportunities for training, developing skills, and engaging in decent work. Because the economic participation rate of women with disabilities is significantly lower compared to men with disabilities (2). As a

result, women with disabilities face far greater obstacles in accessing housing, sanitation services, health, education, job training and employment. And they are also at higher risk of experiencing violence, sexual abuse, neglect, abuse and exploitation. Finally, the researchers wanted to see how discrimination experienced by women workers in disability in the city of Malang.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses the qualitative approach of the Straussian version of the grounded theory method. Data collection uses unstructured interviews, non-participant observation, and FGD (group discussion forum). The selection of participants through the sampling technique used in this research is Purposive Sampling, which determines the sample that matches the research objectives through the characteristics of the sample because the process of coding and data analysis may be subject to distortion because at this stage researchers will select several research subjects that are very stand out and represent. The process of collecting research participants, researchers assisted by other informants by using Snowball Sampling, namely the way informants were found to be willing to refer researchers to other informants (6).

The participants were as many as 10 people, with women totaling 6 people and 4 men. Disabled participants of 4 people consisted of 3 women and 1 male, as well as 5 government informants and 1 person who received disability workers.

III. RESULTS

The results obtained in the data analysis process using the grounded theory method with the Straussian version of the analysis, resulting in discrimination felt by women with disabilities is:

- Covered with fear
- Envy witnesses the struggle of others
- Labeled as a beggar
- Ignorance
- Appreciated as a useless person
- Suffering from persecution
- Survive for life
- Financial difficulties
- Facing challenges for life's well-being
- Trapped at home
- Loss of confidence in yourself

IV. DISCUSSION

In the realm where gender and disability are often linked as part of the results of social construction, for women with

disabilities who get labeled as weak and passive, while on the other hand women with disability get more stereotypical views than men with disabilities due to their dependence, passivity and weakness. The reason is because women with disabilities experience 3 discrimination, first in addition to getting the stigma that they are women and people with disabilities, most of them are in poor condition (poor socially, economically, politically and in other sectors of life) (7). Secondly, in view of femininity, there is a stereotype that women are weak creatures, so that they are distinguished from childhood into various combinations with men or can be called gender bias. Third, the low self-confidence of women in general often lacks respect for their abilities, especially this also happens to women with disabilities.

Furthermore, from this view there is an impact that can be pro and contra due to the psychological relationship between women with disabilities who work. In psychological disability women, especially those working there is a view that when there are shortcomings in health, physical and mental conditions which mainly occur during financial difficulties because the policy of not protecting disability to get income makes a separate impact whether they are in poverty or the policies made by people with disabilities this is useless, cannot face the challenge of how to prepare for their own welfare (8). Another thing that was felt was that there were no jobs or income, one of the other things was making women with disabilities confused and felt they did not want to be trapped inside the house.

Other obstacles include accessibility issues, not only for infrastructure and transportation but also for information and communication services related to work (2). Disabled women experience double discrimination compared to men with disabilities, this is because they are discriminated against by gender, disability, and poor (5).

V. CONCLUSION

The neglect of human values that become social construction has an impact on how people perceive persons with disabilities especially in women with disabilities, the gap in accessibility affects the community itself which disabilities persons, not persons with disabilities who disability them.

Even the life order which considers that women with disabilities need to be pitied affects the psychology of women with disabilities, due to being labeled that they need to be pitied and become a doctrine that women with disabilities are useless.

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